

Get ready to start in a 6-hour Workflow

Before reading this, please read the overview of REDMANE to get a better understanding:

[REDMANE INTERNS README V2.docx](#)

Overview of Workflow team ~ 2 mins

- The main task of the Workflow team is to **(1) generate synthetic data**, which will be **(2) uploaded to the organisations** through Virtual Machines (VM) and then **(3) connect these files to the Data Registry**

Figure 1: Visualisation of the Workflow team

The yellow text was generated by the *data ingestion team* (need to collaborate)

Synthetic data ~ 2 mins

- For the Summer Intake 2026, there are 2 data types that we worked on: **WGS** and **Imaging** datasets, with 2 main types of synthetic data that were generated (called Project 1 and Project 2).
- **Important note:** Our internal team called it Project 2. However, in the REDMANE system (Data registry & Organisation VM), it is called Project 3, hence the **project ids starts with P3-xxx**
- Currently, we have WGS for both Project 1 and 2, but only Project 1 for Imaging.

The aim of this project was to generate synthetic genomic datasets at three hierarchical levels:

1. **Raw sequencing data** – FASTQ
2. **Aligned data** – BAM
3. **Variant-level summary data** – VCF

Project 1 ~ 1 mins

Non-zero files, Correct file naming, binary content (Mimics the real content)

This is generated by using Python (Refer to this [GitHub Repo](#) - note that it is called Project 2 in the Repo). More details on the code are in the Readme file.

In this Project we want the file names to have the sampleid, and we should have a spreadsheet file that maps the sampleids to their patientids

Project 2 ~ 2 mins

Replicate real files/content but synthetically generate.

There are 2 methods for this:

1. Dwaipayan and Kaung Myat
2. Dinesh - What was used for the demo environment, P3, as well as Amanda's tutorial

Generate synthetic genomic datasets at three hierarchical levels (Dwaipayan and Kaung Myat) ~ 4 mins

The datasets were generated from publicly available **Genome in a Bottle (GIAB)** sequencing data. The project also demonstrates an end-to-end Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) analysis pipeline.

1. Theoretical Background

1.1 FASTQ Format (Raw Data Level)

FASTQ is the standard format for raw sequencing reads.

Paired-end sequencing generates two files:

- R1 (forward reads)
- R2 (reverse reads)

2. Alignment (FASTQ → BAM)

Alignment is the process of mapping short sequencing reads to a reference genome to determine their genomic origin.

5.1 BWA Algorithm

Tool used: **BWA (Burrows-Wheeler Aligner)**

Steps in alignment:

1. Reference indexing
2. Read mapping
3. SAM output generation

3. Reference Genome Strategy - Chromosome 22

Reference used:

- Chromosome 22 (GRCh38)
- Size ~50 MB

4. Variant Calling Theory (BAM → VCF)

Variant calling identifies differences between the sequenced sample and the reference genome.

4.1 Variant Calling with bcftools

bcftools call:

- Applies statistical models
- Determines genotype likelihoods
- Outputs VCF

Workflow completed:

FASTQ → SAM → BAM → Sorted BAM → Indexed BAM → mpileup → VCF

Generate synthetic genomic datasets at three hierarchical levels (Dinesh) ~ 4 mins

1. Downloading Raw Dataset

Downloaded publicly available raw paired-end FASTQ files from the Genome in a Bottle project.

Link to GIAB used:

https://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/ReferenceSamples/giab/data/AshkenazimTrio/HG002_NA24385_son/NIST_HiSeq_HG002_Homogeneity-10953946/HG002_HiSeq300x_fastq/140528_D00360_0018_AH8VC6ADXX/Project_RM8391_RM8392/Sample_2A1/

2. Splitting FASTQ Files with Nextflow Workflow

Created a Nextflow workflow to correctly separate and organise multiple Read_1 and Read_2 files.

- Properly paired and structured Read_1 and Read_2 FASTQ files.

Please refer to the GitHub link for this:

https://github.com/dineshkumar741/File_Splitter-for-multiple-Read_1-and-Read_2-files

3. Reference Indexing

The reference genome indexing was executed separately to save time, as indexing can take 1–2 hours and does not need to be repeated.

Input:

- Reference genome FASTA file

Output:

- Indexed reference genome files (.bwt, .pac, .ann, .amb, .sa)

4. Variant Analysis Workflow (Nextflow + Docker)

Developed a second Nextflow workflow (using Docker containers for reproducibility and scalability) covering alignment through final variant annotation.

Please refer to the GitHub link, Technical diary and Tutorial for more details:

Alignment (BWA):

input: Indexed reference genome files + Paired FASTQ

Output: SAM

Sorting & Indexing (Samtools):

Input: SAM

Output: BAM files (.bam, sorted.bam, bam.bai)

Variant Calling (FreeBayes):

Input: BAM files + Indexed reference genome files

Output: Output.VCF

Variant Annotation (SnpEff):

Input: VCF

Output: Annotated.VCF

Visualisation – Integrative Genomics Viewer (IGV):

Open IGV > select Homo Sapiens as your reference genome > Upload sorted.bam files > Observe variants.

Make sure to have the bam.bai file in the same folder.

5. Generated Output Files:

- Indexed reference genome files
- BAM files
- Raw VCF files
- Annotated VCF files

6. Compression and Data Transfer

Please refer to this GitHub link for more details:

<https://github.com/dineshkumar741/Compressing-variant-files-/blob/main/README.md>

Compressed final output files using tar and GSC tools before sharing with the team for upload to a Virtual Machine (VM).

Input:

- Final BAM and annotated VCF files

Output:

- Compressed archive files ready for transfer and VM upload

Synthetic dataset Generation:

Follow the GitHub link for a more detailed tutorial:

<https://github.com/dineshkumar741/Sythetic-fastq-dataset-simulator>

Real sorted.bam & bam.bai file

Project 2 by Osama:

1- Split the files ~ 3 mins

Created an R project to split the fastq files depending on the number of files you want to generate, and decide how many reads per file.

For example ⇒ you have file A with 3M reads inside, and you decided to generate 10 files so, the number of reads per file, and if there are any remaining reads, the program just adds them to the last file generated. That means if there is a remainder will be inside file number 10

2- WGS workflow ~ 3 min

Used bash scripting to generate annotated vcf files ⇒

Uploading to the Organisation VM ~ 2 mins

Once you have the files ready, you will need to upload them to the Organisation via VM. This is done by SSH into the server and using the command line.

Use this document as your tutorial - also contains the next step:

[This tutorial](#)

Connecting files to data registry ~ 1 mins

Once the files are in the organisation, you can start uploading the metadata to the data registry.

Steps:

1. Create a new dataset in the data registry
2. The config.json file will be created from the data registry - currently, this feature is not there yet, hence it must be given by the data ingestion team
3. Upload the config.json and python script to the organisation VM
4. Run the code to produce output.json and output.html
5. Upload output.json to the data registry

Video Tutorial:

[Demo video](#)

Next goal:

- Have a project 2 working for imaging dataset
- Data transfer agreement

Links to documents and GitHub:

- Amanda's Technical Diary - Generating Project 1 dataset (P1-001) and uploading the metadata from the organisation to the data registry:
 - https://docs.google.com/document/d/1PdHh0yenGqtGvS4GU7YxqcZ73ouKVpx7r_4aXuRSjWM/edit?usp=sharing
- Amanda's Tutorial - Uploading the metadata from the organisation to the data registry:
 - https://docs.google.com/document/d/1PemtaQQ8qJiMARqTG3K1YCcYPr7k1mS_TjhlW_P8uQeM/edit?usp=sharing
- Github Repo to generate Project 1 dataset:
 - <https://github.com/eamandaa/Workflow-team-Summer-25>
- Jyoti Technical Diary

- <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1epXLUaC-TSwGMPNjSrpoyAAstWJUqupHsKq9XaQIBRo/edit?tab=t.0>
- Jyoti's Tutorial
 - https://docs.google.com/document/d/e/2PACX-1vRZCDZry_4rt73FxxqQbzbkv2PrKe8AadYJYzsDZ5SuqNPzpSxztsRTXrwrww-RaH25pC5LXIVySVy/pub
- Jyoti GitHub repo
 - <https://github.com/Clinical-Informatics-Collaborative/generatervis>
- Osama's Technical Diary - Workflow of the project and some problems I faced:
 - https://docs.google.com/document/d/1gmMbw76AL_GuyqHRXSYOrdYBwBr_MoOhTxO4MwMqPI0/edit?tab=t.0
- Osama's Tutorial - project 2 splitting Fastq files and generating VCF files:
 - https://docs.google.com/document/d/1AgmBaahmXNn7uAaSX_81irKk0bO1wsfVmQWPFoluQVA/edit?tab=t.
- Osama's Github repo - project 2 splitting Fastq files and generating VCF files:
 - <https://github.com/osama184gamal/separate-Fastq-files>
- Dinesh's Technical diary: Project 2 (Task-3) to generate final Annotated VCF files (ABOO.bam, ABOO_annotated.vcf):
 - <https://wehieduau.sharepoint.com/:w:/r/sites/StudentInternGroupatWEHI/Shared%20Documents/Data%20Commons/2026%20Summer/Technical%20Diary%20Dinesh.docx?d=w78336d51827f43f6afd00f7c4683b31f&csf=1&web=1&e=kaqwga>
- Dinesh's workflow for File Splitting - GitHub link:
 - https://github.com/dineshkumar741/File_Splitter-for-multiple-Read_1-and-Read_2-files
- Dinesh's Tutorial: Project 2 (Task-3) to generate final Annotated VCF files (ABOO.bam, ABOO_annotated.vcf):
 - https://docs.google.com/document/d/1_wyv7becwkY9QC_Dk4GbL5GgMj5ISBpWY0fiV0KsqJM/edit?usp=sharing
- Dinesh's Github link: Project 2 (Task-3) to generate final Annotated VCF files (ABOO.bam, ABOO_annotated.vcf)
 - <https://github.com/dineshkumar741/Variant-calling-workflow/tree/main>
- Dinesh's GitHub link for file compression & decompression:
 - <https://github.com/dineshkumar741/Compressing-variant-files-/blob/main/README.md>
- Dinesh's Synthetic dataset simulator:
 - <https://github.com/dineshkumar741/Sythetic-fastq-dataset-simulator>
- Dinesh's nf-core/SAREK pipeline:
 - <https://github.com/dineshkumar741/Variant-Calling-with-nf-core-sarek>
- Kaung Myat and Dwaipayan's Technical Diary contains Linux commands for executing the workflow:
 - <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1tyellgYg1vD6BbWofyBtAnmfbdvtvQdEHIJi6ia2uLow/edit?usp=sharing>
- The Raw files from Genome in a Bottle:
 - https://ftp-trace.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/ReferenceSamples/giab/data_indexes/As_hkenazimTrio/sequence.index.AJtrio_Illumina300X_wgs_07292015_updated.HG002